

LONG ABSTRACT

Ten lessons learned on improving the open data reusability of bioinformatics knowledge bases

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Short Abstract

Background, enhancing interoperability of bioinformatics knowledge bases is a high priority requirement to maximize open data reusability, and thus increase their utility such as the return on investment for biomedical research. A knowledge base may provide useful information for life scientists and other knowledge bases, but it only acquires exchange value once the knowledge base is (re)used, and without interoperability the utility lies dormant. **Results**, in this talk, we discuss several approaches to boost interoperability depending on the interoperable parts. The findings are driven by several real-world scenario examples that were mostly implemented by Bgee, a well-established gene expression database. Moreover, we discuss ten general main lessons learnt. These lessons can be applied in the context of any bioinformatics knowledge base to foster open data reusability. **Conclusions**, this work provides pragmatic methods and transferable skills to promote reusability of bioinformatics knowledge bases by focusing on interoperability.

Key words: Interoperability; databases; data reusability; ontologies; FAIR principles

Long Abstract

Bioinformatics knowledge bases (KB) are often built to serve a specific community of interest. By providing software tools, methods, services and data, these KBs aim to facilitate and to provide the means for their users' work, such as scientific research. Therefore, the notion of reusability (i.e., the capability of a resource to be used multiple times by distinct agents) is an important aspect to be considered by any bioinformatics KB.

In this talk, among several similar and complementary definitions of interoperability, we consider the following definition of interoperability: "the ability of two or more systems or elements to exchange information and to use the information that has been exchanged". Based on this definition, and looking at bioinformatics KBs as systems, we will describe how to improve reusability through interoperability enhancement. It is important to notice that we do not seek in this work to discuss all aspects of the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principles, although we aim at being compliant with them and beyond to achieve an optimal reusability. We focus on the interoperability aspect because without it, for instance, it will be hard or even impossible to be findable and accessible. For example, assigning persistent identifiers or descriptive metadata for digital resources, respectively F1 and F2 principles, will only be useful if they are interoperable. This is because for a persistent identifier to be resolved, it will need to interoperate with other systems such as the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) resolver. This is also why when talking about DOI, we emphasize it is a persistent *interoperable* identifier, that complies with the ISO 26324:2012 standard. Similarly, the produced descriptive metadata will only be useful, for example, to a search engine, if it can be consumed, that is interoperable.

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Figure 1. A simplified illustration of the boost of the Bgee interoperability network. The elements in the inner circle are examples of the ensemble of techniques used to implement the Bgee interoperability with diverse databases and systems, that are illustrated with their logos in the outer circle.

Therefore, to describe how to develop a more reusable KB, in this talk, we will focus on pragmatic approaches for interoperability enhancement, and we will illustrate these approaches with Bgee. Bgee is a well-established database to retrieve and compare gene expression patterns in multiple animal species. It integrates and harmonises multiple data sources that are based on heterogeneous techniques, namely, single-cell RNA-Seq (scRNA-Seq), bulk RNA-Seq, Affymetrix, in situ hybridization, and Expressed Sequence Tags (EST). It is based exclusively on curated healthy wild-type expression data (e.g., no gene knock-out, no treatment, no disease), to provide a comparable reference of normal gene expression. Although we centre on our work on the Bgee use case, the practices, methods and lessons learnt discussed here are transferable to other KBs.

Enhancing interoperability: the Bgee use case. The Bgee KB integrates and aggregates data from heterogeneous data sources by reconciling them and applying a data warehouse approach, resulting in a large relational database of about 8TB at time of writing. Curation and quality control are at the core of the Bgee mission. Moreover, being licensed as a public domain database makes Bgee an interesting case study for boosting interoperability since no ownership restrictions exist when reusing its data. Fig. 1 shows a simplified view of a portion of the Bgee interoperability network boost and of the technologies involved. We applied different methods to build this network, that are summarised as one-side, two-side and multi-side interoperability approaches, see definitions Def. 1, Def. 2, and Def. 3.

Definition 1. *One-side interoperability: one side must strictly comply with the other's procedure to interoperate. There is no or little possible negotiation between interoperable parts.*

Definition 2. *Two-side interoperability: both sides must reconcile with each other, that is to establish a common agreement to interoperate.*

Definition 3. *Multi-side interoperability: the two or more sides that want to interoperate comply with an independent interoperability procedure. Improvements or changes in this procedure may be upon request and may or may not be accepted by the third-party organisation or community that maintains the interoperability procedure.*

Ten lessons learned. Below we summarise the lessons learned to improve open data reusability of bioinformatics KBs:

- Lesson 1.** Partial interoperability is better than none.
- Lesson 2.** Iteratively improve the information exchange rather than trying to achieve full interoperability at once.
- Lesson 3.** Reusability implies better visibility, and vice-versa.
- Lesson 4.** Interoperability requires maintenance.
- Lesson 5.** Automate interoperability as much as possible
- Lesson 6.** Be flexible when choosing and providing interoperability approaches.
- Lesson 7.** Focus on knowledge base delegates.
- Lesson 8.** There is a positive domino effect of knowledge base interoperability.
- Lesson 9.** Adopt the most appropriated license.
- Lesson 10.** Provide documentation, training, and tutorials for interoperability.

Conclusion. We argue that the best interoperability approach is the one that gets implemented despite partial interoperability or dissent between KB representatives. Therefore, one-, two- and multi-side interoperability methods are all relevant to promote KB data (re)use. Nevertheless, providing and implementing one or more of these methods should not be considered as final solutions for interoperability. This is because KBs, information exchange technologies and practices evolve.